

COMPOSITE MATERIALS AT THE CROSSROADS – TRANSITION TO AFFORDABILITY

Cecil W. Schneider

*Lockheed Martin Aeronautical Systems
86 South Cobb Drive, Marietta, Georgia 30063-0648 USA*

SUMMARY: Historical development of composite materials, trends for aerospace and non-aerospace applications, and obstacles to expanded application to aerospace products are addressed in this paper. While high performance composite materials, using carbon fiber in a polymer matrix, have matured over the past 30 years, affordable application of these materials has eluded the aerospace industry. Over the past few years, the aerospace industry and government have devoted significant resources to development of innovative manufacturing processes to reduce costs, but composite designs are still significantly more expensive than those with comparable metallic structures. This paper addresses some of the deterrents to affordable composite structures, with recommendations for future development to overcome the affordability obstacles.

KEYWORDS: design-for-manufacturing, composite manufacturing, composites affordability, composites development requirements, composite applications, trends in composites development

INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix composites became structurally viable aerospace materials with the development of carbon fibers in the 1960s. As the technology matured in the 1970s the development focus was on performance, driven by a need to save weight on high performance fighter and V/STOL aircraft. Design and analysis methods were developed, refined and validated, providing the capability for design of large, complex aircraft structures with a high degree of confidence. During the 1980s the technology emphasis shifted from performance to cost reduction, while still maintaining high performance. The industry also began to integrate composite materials into stealth aircraft to reduce the radar signature of fighter and bomber aircraft. While usage of composite materials was still driven by the U.S. Department of Defense [DoD] vehicles, there began to be increasing applications to non-aerospace products such as high-end sporting goods.

During the past decade, there has been a dramatic shift towards affordability in aircraft application priorities, which has driven the development focus to lower cost materials and processes. The industry assessed lessons learned from development and production programs, with the result that increased emphasis must be placed on design and manufacturing integration to develop design-for-manufacturing guidelines and tools. Development activities in advanced manufacturing automation such as fiber placement and Resin Transfer Molding [RTM] are leading to significant reductions in manufacturing cost. The rapid expansion of composite material applications came to a sudden end in the early

1990's with the rapid downsizing of DoD, and subsequent termination of many government programs. These changes led to mutual recognition among users, suppliers and government that some degree of standardization of materials specification, testing, and design properties could achieve significant reductions in cost. This downturn has been reversed in the past two years as other, non-aerospace, industries have increased their applications of advanced composite materials. Because of this, future growth of the carbon fiber market will not be in military aircraft, but in commercial products with selective use of composite materials.

HISTORICAL PERSPECTIVE

The use of *composite* materials on aircraft structures is not a recent event. *Composite* aircraft structures were around even before powered flight since early gliders [Figure 1] and the Wright Flyer (which achieved the first powered flight at Kitty Hawk) were fabricated of fabric over wood, with only limited use of metal in critical areas. It was not until the thirties that aluminum took over as a primary aircraft structural material as aircraft sought ever higher speed and performance levels. The first all-aluminum aircraft was the Lockheed *Electra*, which was first delivered to airlines in 1934. Not surprisingly, those early metal applications encountered significant resistance from design and manufacturing personnel toward this 'new-fangled' aluminum material.

Fig. 1: Otto Lilienthal, 1891

While fiberglass/epoxy materials were in general use on aircraft for non-structural applications during the 1950's and 60's, there were not considered to be a structural material because of the low properties and strength-to-weight ratios. Advanced composite structures became a reality with the development of carbon fibers in the 1960's. As these materials were introduced, the development community had to overcome early problems to develop fibers, resins and prepregs that achieved strength and modulus properties that outperformed aluminum materials, while still contending with the real-world environmental and moisture concerns and issues. Just as with the introduction of aluminum materials, composite materials brought new concerns and issues to the design process as well as cultural bias about putting "burned materials on airplanes". Early concerns about the moisture intrusion [Figure 2] were resolved by development of "hot/wet" testing that accounts for the "knock-down" factors in design properties.

Fig. 2: Moisture Was An Early Concern

Fig.3: L-1011 Composite Aileron

As the technology matured in the 1970's, development activities continued to have a performance emphasis, driven by a need to save weight on high performance military fighter and V/STOL aircraft. The focus was on continued development of advanced materials to achieve higher modulus and strength to further reduce weight, with very little emphasis on affordability. Design methods were developed, refined and validated to provide capabilities for design of aircraft structures with a

high degree of confidence. However, composite materials still required a high level of development and qualification testing to get initial secondary structural applications into production. Most of the composite structures produced during this period were limited quantity runs of secondary structures to prove feasibility and obtain initial customer confidence by conducting flight evaluations. Much of these initial flight evaluation structures were fabricated under contracts from NASA [Figures 3 and 4] and the U.S. Air Force Wright Laboratories.

Fig. 4: L-1011 Composite Vertical Fin

During the 1980's we began to see a shift to increasing emphasis on cost reduction, while still maintaining high performance. Initial production applications of secondary structures in the early part of the decade led to application on primary structures on fighters, V/STOL and business aircraft by the end of the 1980's. Through development efforts led by NASA, advanced composite materials were transitioned to initial commercial aircraft secondary structures. However, DoD applications continued to predominate, with optimistic forecasts of usage that lead material suppliers to facilitate and develop new fiber, resin and prepreg products. The result was an expanding line of available capacity and products, but with little standardization. Manufacturing technology scale-up and automation development activities were concentrated on cost reduction. However, many of these efforts were limited in scope by focusing only on specific narrow technology areas while overlooking design or tooling aspects. The industry began to integrate composite materials into the stealth world to achieve low observable characteristics -- although most of us did not know this was occurring at the time. The majority of the structure on the B-2 Bomber [Figure 5] was fabricated from carbon/epoxy materials, coated to reduce radar signature. While production of composite materials was still driven by DoD applications, we began to see increasing application to non-aerospace products such as high-end sporting goods -- for example, golf clubs and tennis rackets.

Fig. 5: B-2 Bomber Is Mostly Composite

In the 1990's, applications have expanded into primary structures on large commercial aircraft, such as the Airbus A-320 and Boeing 777 tail structures [Figure 6]. During this decade, there has been a dramatic shift towards affordability in aircraft application priorities, which has driven the development focus toward lower cost materials and processes. The industry assessed lessons learned from development and production programs, with the result that additional development effort is required for design and manufacturing integration,

leading to design-for-manufacturing guidelines and tools. Development of advanced manufacturing automation such as fiber placement and RTM has provided fabrication processes that can significantly reduce manufacturing cost, but there is still work remaining to develop and validate optimized design methods for these processes. The proliferation of composite materials in the late 1980's came to a sudden end in the early 1990's with the rapid downsizing of DoD, and subsequent termination of many government programs. These changes led to mutual recognition among the users, suppliers and government that some degree of standardization of materials specification, testing and design properties could achieve significant reductions in cost. As the DoD usage of composite materials dramatically decreased, the supplier industry was hard hit by reductions in demand for fiber and resin.

Fig. 6: Boeing 777 Tail Structure

The Changing Environment

During the past decade, there have been dramatic changes in health and safety considerations for all materials, which has produced a much safer working environment. In the past, health and safety would be considered only after evaluating materials for performance. Today, hazardous materials are rapidly being replaced with environmentally friendly materials and processes to reduce workplace exposure. Health and safety must be evaluated prior to introduction of materials into the shops, with safe handling procedures written into the specifications prior to purchase. This has had an impact on materials development as well as applications, but the net result is a much safer working environment for employees.

Government And Industry Trends

Starting in the mid-1980's, DoD budgets began to decrease, and dramatically dropped after the collapse of the Soviet Union [Figure 7]. We have not yet seen the end of this decrease in budgets, which drastically reduced the number of airframe program new starts. The number of aerospace companies has also dramatically decreased through mergers and buyouts, and teaming on large companies has become the norm. In 1945 there were 16 major U.S. companies building military aircraft. This had reduced to 11 in 1980, 9 in 1985, 6 in 1990 and three today. With fewer aircraft programs, the demand for carbon fiber dropped, causing material suppliers to decrease their R&D investment. Today there are few new materials being developed, and most of those that are under development are focused on commercial rather than military products.

Fig. 7: DoD Budget Trends

While the decreasing DoD budgets led to consolidation changes in airframe companies, there

have been similar changes in the material supplier industry. Shipments of composite prepreg started slowing in 1989, causing ripples in an industry that had been growing at 20-25% per year. The downturn in material orders led to consolidation of the material suppliers, resulting in companies exiting the industry, bankruptcies, and buyouts. The bottom was reached in 1993, and the industry is again experiencing growth, but most of this growth is in the commercial marketplace. However, the carbon fiber suppliers are not repeating past practices of over-facilitating, which has created long lead times for carbon fiber since demand is currently exceeding capacity.

THE FUTURE PARADIGM

While the industry has been downsizing, right-sizing, consolidating and merging the U.S. government has been also been undergoing similar change. DoD initiatives are underway on conversion from government to commercial standards and specifications as well as commercial contracting practices, all of which will impact the way we procure and use materials and how we process these materials. DoD has also been evaluating the requirements for future air vehicles under their Fixed Wing Vehicle Program. The government/industry team established that affordability issues are the key design drivers, regardless of aircraft type. Requirements that drive affordability include reduced fabrication cost, reductions in development span, and reduced operational and support costs. However, requirements for reduced weight, increased fatigue life and higher structural operating temperatures are still valid design drivers that must be met with affordable designs.

F-22 Material Applications

The impact of affordability on materials decisions during the design process can be seen in the use of composite materials on the F-22 Advanced Tactical Fighter [Figure 8]. During the proposal stage on this program, the aircraft used about 40% composites to meet performance, temperature and toughness requirements. As the design progressed through successive trade studies, the amount of composite materials decreased to approximately 25% today. This reduction reflects the ever-increasing emphasis on affordability over performance – even for high performance fighter aircraft. While performance is obviously still important, the price that a program is willing to pay for this performance is lower than it was in the past.

Fig. 8: F-22 Material Applications

Design for affordability must be incorporated early in the design process to be effective. This requires better Integrated Product and Process Development [IPPD] methods and tools to permit the Integrated Product Teams [IPT] to be able to perform collaborative design and analysis among all disciplines, including manufacturing and inspection. These tools must be integrated with the business and financial systems to provide optimized design-for-manufacturing methods that integrate scheduling and cost with performance. Development of

IPPD tools is an ongoing effort at university, industry and government labs, but much more needs to be done to achieve a true virtual enterprise that is capable of supporting design at remote sites. The methods being developed must be transferred to industry development teams to fully integrate them into design tools that can be readily used by the design teams. Training of the design teams is also a critical factor that the methodology should address so that *Tutorials* are built into the software programs. The amount of time and schedule that is required to adequately train new personnel must be minimized – this should be provided via on-line training modules that are an integral part of the methods.

Design Paradigm Must Change

In addition to the development of verified collaborative IPPD tools, industry must change the approach to design for composite materials to achieve true affordability. Today, a typical airframe design is made up of lots of *bits and pieces*. The design decisions that lead us down this path are driven by many things -- a lack of knowledge on how to design for the material or process, inadequate or incomplete design tools, *tug-of-wars* and *turf-battles* between different organizations, etc.

In the example shown in Figure 9, a concept aircraft was redesigned for affordability only, resulting in a 94% reduction in parts count and a 95% reduction in fastener count. While this example is overly simplistic, it does show that affordability can be achieved by a dramatic reduction in part count and assembly operations. Development of innovative design approaches and IPPD tools that can be easily used by the entire IPT will enable design teams to achieve this parts consolidation and thereby reduce the cost of composite structures to the point that they are comparable with conventional metallic structures. Only then will we see the use of composites on aircraft structure reverse the downward trend in terms of percent use.

Fig: 9: Design For Affordability Involves Reduced Part Count And Assembly [1]

TECHNOLOGY NEEDS

Over the past two years, representatives of aerospace companies and Wright Laboratories reviewed past development and production programs on composite materials and structures to determine the deterrents to affordability. The primary findings of this study can be divided into design/analysis and materials/structures issues, which are itemized in the following subsections.

Design and Analysis Methods

There is a need within the industry for standardized automated design, analysis, modeling and simulation methods for composite structures that provide:

- A design database of materials properties and specifications prior to start of detail design. This will take a cooperative effort on the part of government and industry. Standardized design data and specifications are needed to provide Mil-Handbook properties (Design Allowables) on composite materials prior to initiation of the design cycle. These design properties must be based on standardized test methods so that all material properties can be compared equally.
- Standardized structural analysis methods that are available for everyone to use. With teaming the norm these days, we need easily used design and analysis methods that are available to multiple-company teams. These methods could then also be used for non-aerospace composite products.
- Design and analysis methods that include physics-based modeling and simulation techniques that cover the range from initial design to fabrication and assembly. With these tools, the design IPT can validate the design prior to release of the design drawings.
- Design-for-manufacturing tools include validated models for material processing, producibility, tool design and manufacturing planning functions. These must allow simplified custom modeling of the design in the IPT environment to provide early detail knowledge. The final output from the IPT should be a "*Build-To Package*" that includes the validated design, all Numerical Control programs, shop planning and operations instructions, inspection steps, tool designs, etc.

Some of these tools exist today, but they do not work together in an IPT environment. Many others need additional research and development and validation. The design tools need to be optimized for large unitized structures that reduce part count to eliminate or minimize tooling and assembly. Large unitized structures are an essential step to affordable composite structures, but the tools for design of such integrated structures are a long way from reality.

Composite Materials and Structures

Lower cost materials and material preforms are other key factors to achieving affordability with composite materials. The material suppliers are working toward \$5/lb carbon fibers for commercial applications -- can these low cost fibers be selectively used for aircraft applications? The aerospace industry has worked on out-of-autoclave curing resins and processes for the past twenty years, but has largely ignored these developments on production applications. Improved resins for lower temperature and pressure cure can reduce the cost of curing composite structures through simplified tooling and lower cost tooling materials. Recent developments in textile preforms also show promise of reducing cost while enhancing out-of-plane loading capabilities. Aligned discontinuous fibers have the capability to be laid out in flat patterns and subsequently post-formed into complex shapes, but development of the material with epoxy resins has stalled and needs to be resumed. Automated fiber placement has made significant progress over the past few years with the concurrent development of towpreg materials. But there is a need for epoxy or thermoplastic resins that will permit real-time cure or consolidation on-the-fly to achieve further improvements in this fabrication

process. In-situ curing resins could eliminate in-process debulk and consolidation cycles that greatly increase fabrication times for thick-section composite structures.

Closed-loop process controls are required to reduce cure cycle time and errors and improve quality of the product. Improved quality will reduce costs and eliminate rework, and provide data for resolution of problems if there anomalies in the cycle.

Innovative structural approaches are needed that will yield large unitized structures that can reduce assembly time and cost. As mentioned previously, the design and analysis methods must be capable of optimizing such designs.

While the industry has made significant progress in automation of the fabrication process, there is still a need for further improvements. Flexible automation for fabrication and assembly is required that is electronically coupled to the design data base. For each fabrication and assembly method there must be compatible process models that can be used for simulation of the entire process.

Trends In Collaboration

In the past we tended to keep everything we developed proprietary, with little sharing of data between companies. We each developed our own analysis methods, data and other tools and convinced ourselves that these provided our competitive edge. With increased teaming among the remaining aerospace companies, there are few secrets in this arena. In the past we each had adequate staff and budget to develop and maintain our methods and databases because there were always multiple production programs to support the technology base, but in today's business environment companies are investing significantly lower levels of funding in research and development, with the result that there are inadequate resources to support all of the required development activities.

We must learn to share data and information that is pre-competitive, and to maintain as proprietary only that data and information that is product related. With fewer and fewer new program starts, industry and government must learn to collaborate on the pre-competitive data and information to reduce the cost of future airframes for both DoD and commercial programs. If we can reduce the cost of airframe products, then we'll see more and more spin-off applications to commercial products.

APPLICATION TO COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS

The technology needs covered here must be addressed in a cooperative spirit between university, industry and government. If we work together to develop, validate and transition the data and methods to industrial programs then we can look forward to a future where we see dramatic increases in the application of composite materials to a wide variety of commercial products that can improve our quality of life and lower the cost of products we

Fig. 11: Commercial Applications Are Rapidly Increasing

procure. If we continue the ways of the past, and do not solve the affordability issues, then we can look forward to a future with diminishing use of composite materials, used only where the customer is willing to pay the premium for increased performance. We know that there are many applications where composites can be applied to increase performance, reduce weight, increase operating life, etc., if composites could be applied at equal or lower cost to other alternative materials. At least one business aircraft employed composite materials for a majority of its structure, but this

extensive use of composite materials increased the price of the aircraft sufficiently to make it unaffordable. Affordable composite designs and processes would have improved the sales potential in these cases. Applications such as bridge reinforcement for better earthquake resistance, lightweight bridges, bicycle and motorbike frames, automobile and truck frames, wind turbines, rail car frames and trucks, golf shafts, tennis rackets, etc., [Figures 10 and 11] provide us with the opportunity to apply composites to reduce weight and increase performance. If only a fraction of these opportunities are exploited, the volume of composite materials used will literally explode overnight – but not many of these opportunities can be exploited if the cost of fabricated components and parts is not decreased. It is up to us collectively to make this future one where composites are the most affordable solution to any design problem.

Fig. 10: Wind Turbines And Blades Are High Potential Application

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